

Autonomous underwater environment perceiving and modeling: an experimental campaign with FeelHippo AUV for Forward Looking Sonar-based Automatic Target Recognition and Data Association

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Abstract—Seabed inspection is one of the most sought-after applications for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs). In particular, acoustic sensors, as Side Scan Sonars (SSSs) and Forward-Looking Sonars (FLSs), are commonly favored over optical cameras to carry out such a task being not influenced by the illumination conditions and providing high-range data. However, acoustic images are often hard to interpret with conventional automatic techniques, forcing human operators to analyze thousands of collected images to identify the so-called Objects of Potential Interest (OPIs). In this perspective, this paper reports the development of an Automatic Target Recognition (ATR) methodology to identify and localize OPIs in FLS imagery; such detections have been then exploited to realize a world model with the Probabilistic Multiple Hypothesis Anchoring (PMHA) data association algorithm. Both the ATR and world modeling systems were on-field tested at the Naval Support and Experimentation Centre (Centro di Supporto e Sperimentazione Navale - CSSN) basin, in La Spezia, Italy, in a multi-vehicle architecture by employing an acoustic channel between FeelHippo AUV and an autonomous moving buoy.

Index Terms—Marine Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Automatic Target Recognition, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles, Convolutional Neural Networks, Underwater Surveillance

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the demanded tasks for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) have become more and more challenging, researchers and scientists are investigating the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in the marine environment [1]. Indeed, accurately perceiving and understanding the environment is a fundamental hierarchical step to accomplish complicated subsea tasks, such as autonomous inspection, exploration planning and/or surveillance. To these scopes, Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) can be equipped with several

acoustic payload sensors, such as Side Scan Sonars (SSSs) and Forward Looking Sonars (FLSs); nevertheless, acoustic images generally present relevant noise and lack of features making the images hard to interpret by using conventional image processing techniques. As a consequence, a human operator is usually in charge of analyzing the thousands of acquired images to identify the so-called Objects of Potential Interest (OPIs). In this view, an Automatic Target Recognition (ATR) strategy that detects and localizes OPIs in FLS imagery hence represents an important tool that could help human operators in this demanding and time-consuming task. Moreover, as long as a large set of OPI detections and localizations is provided, the need for a world modeling methodology, containing a dynamically updated list of 3D geolocalized objects, does arise as pivotal. Indeed, the major purpose of such a technique is constituted by providing a unique, unified representation of the whole gamma of existing objects of interest in the surveyed area; in other words, if the same target is detected and localized several times, the world modeling algorithm aims at fusing the supplied information into a single world model object.

II. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Driven by these considerations, an ATR strategy for FLS frames has been designed and implemented to detect and geolocalize potential targets of interest placed on the seabed. Besides, the several detections, supplied by the ATR system, have been employed to create a world model of 3D-localized and labeled OPIs. Firstly, the selected Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, SSD Mobilenet V2, has been trained by exploiting a custom gathered dataset of heterogeneous images, acquired in May 2019 at the Naval Support and Ex-

Fig. 1. On the left, FeelHippo AUV before an on-field underwater mission in Vulcano island, Italy. On the right, the autonomous moving buoy during an on-field mission at the CSSN basin, La Spezia, Italy.

perimentation Centre (Centro di Supporto e Sperimentazione Navale - CSSN) basin in La Spezia (Italy), and the open-source machine learning library TensorFlow. Subsequently, the trained neural network has been incorporated into a custom ATR software, developed in the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework. Aiming to develop an onboard, pragmatically working ATR solution for compact AUVs, an NVIDIA Jetson Nano has been selected as dedicated payload hardware for running the trained CNN model, and it was mounted on FeelHippo AUV [2].

Finally, the ATR with world modeling solution has been validated online in October 2020 with two vehicles (Fig. 1) both developed by the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence (UNIFI DIEF): FeelHippo AUV (equipped with a small towed buoy as Wi-Fi bridge), and an autonomous moving buoy [3], working as surface vessel and capable of Wi-Fi as well as acoustic communication. The two involved vehicles have been together employed during an experimental campaign performed within the activities of the SEALab, the joint research laboratory between the CSSN of the Italian Navy and the Interuniversity Center of Integrated Systems for the Marine Environment (ISME).

More in detail, the FLS images were acquired and processed online with the developed embedded ATR solution by FeelHippo AUV (Fig. 2). In order to provide a visual feedback (not available from an acoustic link), the detected targets and their estimated positions, outcomes of the ATR strategy, were additionally streamed in real-time using the small towed buoy, physically linked to FeelHippo AUV, to a workstation where a human operator could supervise the process. At the same time, FeelHippo AUV acoustically transmitted the same ATR results to the autonomous buoy, which also worked as a Wi-Fi bridge to a workstation running a specifically customized version of the Probabilistic Multiple Hypothesis Anchoring (PMHA) data association algorithm [4] to generate and maintain a consistent world state estimate. As the last stage, the developed data association solution allowed to model the perceived environment by deciding whether the detected OPIs had already been discovered or not and creating a world model symbolic representation of 3D-localized, uniquely labeled objects (Fig.

3 and Table I).

Fig. 2. Examples of the online detected and localized OPIs by means of the developed self-contained ATR with the SSD network during the experimental campaign conducted in October 2020 at the CSSN, La Spezia, Italy. In purple the localization outcomes in a Latitude-Longitude-Depth representation whilst in green the bounding box traced around the OPIs as well as the class label and the detection probability.

TABLE I
PHMA OUTCOMES: NUMBER OF DETECTIONS FOR EACH OPI OBJECT AND RELATIVE COVARIANCE

OPIs	Number of detections	σ_x (m)	σ_y (m)
OPI1	3	0.17	0.13
OPI2	8	0.91	0.44
OPI3	10	1.46	0.88
OPI4	8	0.34	0.51
OPI5	5	0.13	0.14
OPI6	10	0.68	0.84
OPI7	6	0.44	0.38
OPI8	2	0.06	0.07
OPI9	7	0.52	0.62

III. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a multi-vehicle ATR with data association architecture aimed at autonomously perceiving and modeling the surrounding underwater environment. Thanks to the developed ATR methodology, FeelHippo AUV was able to identify and localize online as well as onboard several OPIs whose ATR results were employed to create a representation of the surveyed world. As a summarizing statement, the achieved results have highlighted the capability for the proposed architecture to autonomously inspect an unknown underwater scenario by effectively detect, localize targets of interest and realizing a multi-object world model.

Fig. 3. Effect of the world modeling process achieved by employing the PMHA algorithm over the whole detection set during the experimental campaign. In a *red* line, the lawnmower path achieved by FeelHippo AUV in a standard survey mission; every path waypoint is illustrated with a *black* dotted circle. On the left, in dotted *yellow* circles, the data association outcomes are outlined with the dedicated OPI detections; finally, *yellow* crosses are employed to describe rejected detections which, indeed, represent two false OPI detections provided by the ATR architecture. On the right, the OPIs representing the world model objects are described by small *blue* circles.

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